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Design Applications in Italian Regions

The average increase was 4.53% between 2018 and 2023.

European Innovation Scoreboard calculates design applications in Italian regions based on GDP. The indicator consists of a ratio. The numerator presents the number of design applications filed with the European Union Intellectual Property Office, while the denominator is the GDP in Purchasing Power Standards. Design applications refer to the appearance of a product or part of it resulting from the lines, contours, colors, shape, texture, materials, and/or its ornamentation. Any industrial or handcrafted object, including packaging, graphic symbols, and typefaces, except computer programs, can be considered a product. It also includes products composed of multiple components that can be disassembled and reassembled. Design protection is directly enforceable in each member state and includes the possibility of an unregistered or registered Community design right for an area that includes all member states. The data refer to Italian regions from 2018 to 2023.

Design applications in Italian regions in 2023. The analysis of design applications in various Italian regions for the year 2023 provides an interesting snapshot of the country's creative and industrial dynamics. These data, representing the frequency of new design registrations, offer a broad spectrum of how different regions contribute to aesthetic and functional innovation in the national economic and productive context. The regions of Friuli Venezia Giulia, Marche, Umbria, and Veneto stand out with the highest values, all exceeding 150, indicating a strong inclination towards sectors such as furniture, industrial design, and fashion, where design is crucial. These regions, in particular, host some of Italy's excellences in terms of design and manufacturing, contributing not only to the local economy but also to Italy's international prestige in these fields. Emilia Romagna, with a value of 148.70, is confirmed as another key center for design innovation, supported by the presence of mechanical and automotive industries, where design plays a key role in the added value of products. This high value is also the result of regional policies that have been promoting investment in R&D and collaboration between universities and industries for years. Conversely, regions like Molise, Calabria, and Sardinia show the lowest values, below 40, suggesting lower activity in the field of registered design. This could reflect an economic fabric with a lower concentration of industries closely related to design or a lower propensity for formal innovation in local products. Even Campania and Sicily, despite their rich artisanal and creative traditions, show relatively modest numbers, perhaps indicating a need for more support in terms of design registration incentive policies. Lombardy and Tuscany, with values of 117.20 and 113.94 respectively, are well-positioned, reflecting their importance as centers of fashion, design, and luxury. These regions benefit from an entrepreneurial climate that values and invests in design as a differentiating and competitive element. Also interesting is the case of Basilicata, which surprises with a high value of 97.20. This figure could

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indicate a specific regional policy aimed at promoting design as an economic development lever or the presence of specific entrepreneurial realities strongly focused on aesthetic innovation. In conclusion, the 2023 data on design applications in Italy show a varied map, with some regions excelling and others lagging. This landscape suggests the opportunity for a more coordinated national policy that can raise the overall level of design innovation through incentives, training, and business support, especially in less developed areas. Incentive policies could not only increase the number of registrations but also stimulate greater integration of design into the local industry, thus contributing to economic recovery and Italy's international competitiveness.

Design applications in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023. Particularly noteworthy is the exponential growth in Basilicata, with a 103.29% increase in applications, rising from 47.81 to 97.20. This massive increase could result from regional policies aimed at promoting innovation or a growing focus on the design sector as an economic development driver. The transformation could also be fueled by the arrival of new companies or the birth of start-ups focused on design. In contrast, regions like Molise and Valle d'Aosta have seen significant decreases in their design applications, with -30.86% and -17.41%, respectively. These declines could reflect a variety of factors, including a lack of institutional support, a decrease in industrial activity, or simply regional economic cycles that have seen a reduction in investment in the design sector. Other regions, such as Campania and Lombardy, have shown slight declines in design applications, perhaps suggesting a stabilization after periods of growth or the maturation of local design markets. In these areas, it may be necessary to renew attention and support to creative industries to stimulate growth again. Regions like Friuli Venezia Giulia and Veneto, which have maintained or shown minimal variations in their design applications, could instead be well-established as centers of excellence in design, maintaining solidity in the number of applications thanks to a strong and consolidated industrial base that continues to innovate without major upheavals. The situation in regions like Emilia Romagna and Tuscany shows moderate but steady growth, suggesting an environment where design innovation is constantly supported and valued. These regions could benefit from a robust and diversified industrial fabric that includes fashion, interior design, and the automotive industry, all sectors that require a constant flow of new designs. Interesting is the case of regions like Puglia and Trentino Alto Adige, which have seen substantial growth of 29.85% and 22.23%, respectively. This could indicate a new focus on design as a distinctive element and competitive advantage in national and international markets.

Design applications in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of design applications in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 reveals interesting dynamics reflecting different trends in regional innovation and creativity. These data show how various areas of the country have responded to economic and cultural stimuli in terms of design, offering an overview of change and growth in this sector. In particular, the South shows a remarkable and steady increase in design applications, growing from 48.24 in 2018 to 55.66 in 2023, with an absolute increase of 7.41 and a growth percentage of 15.36%. This increase can be interpreted as the result of strengthened interest and investment in creative and design industries, perhaps driven by new innovation support policies or an increase in economic activities that require a strong design element. The growth in the South could also reflect a recovery strategy compared to other regions more traditionally associated with design innovation, such as the North and Center. In contrast, the North has shown surprising stability, with an almost zero absolute variation (-0.01) and a zero percentage variation (-0.01%). This suggests that the region may have reached a sort of saturation or stabilization in its ability to generate new design applications, or that Northern industries are in a phase of consolidation rather than expansion. The lack of growth could also indicate acute competitiveness and a struggle for

innovation, where maintaining the status quo is already a challenge. The Center has seen moderate growth, with an increase in design applications from 117.56 in 2018 to 122.43 in 2023, registering an absolute increase of 4.88 and a growth percentage of 4.15%. This growth, although not dramatic, indicates a continued evolution and interest in the design sector, possibly fueled by a robust economic environment and a well-established presence of academic institutions and research centers promoting innovation. The differences in growth trends between these macro-regions may be influenced by various factors, including the type of predominant industries in each region, regional innovation support policies, access to educational and creative resources, and the availability of investments in research and development. The South, for example, may now benefit from greater attention to incentive policies that have stimulated creativity and innovation in response to a previously lower base of activity in the design sector.

North-South Divide. The analysis of design applications in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 reveals a significant growth dynamic in the South, unlike the North, which shows substantial stasis. This scenario offers a magnifying lens on potential regional disparities and their implications for economic development and innovation. The South recorded a remarkable 15.36% increase in design applications, growing from 48.24 in 2018 to 55.66 in 2023. This increase suggests a growing vitality in the design sector, which could be stimulated by various factors including improved infrastructure, the implementation of more effective incentive policies, or a growing recognition of the importance of design in the local economy. The increase could also reflect a change in the South's industrial fabric, with a growing focus on sectors such as tourism, furniture, and consumer goods, which are design-intensive. In stark contrast, the North shows a statistical anomaly with an almost zero percentage variation (-0.01%). Despite being traditionally Italy's economic and industrial locomotive, with a strong concentration of manufacturing and design industries, the North has not registered significant growth in design applications during the period in question. This could indicate market saturation or perhaps increased competition that prevents net growth in new design registrations. The Center, with moderate growth of 4.15%, positions itself between the South and the North, suggesting stability in the design sector, supported by a balanced economic environment and a diversity of industries that continue to invest in design innovation. These data highlight an apparent North-South divide in the context of design applications in Italy. While the North seems to be facing a phase of stasis or maturity, the South is emerging as a new growth center for design. This trend could have significant implications for economic and regional development policies. For example, it might be necessary to renew strategies in the North to revive innovation, while in the South, it might be appropriate to support and capitalize on the current growth momentum through further investments and incentives.

Economic Policies. To increase design applications in Italian regions, it is essential to implement economic policies that stimulate innovation, support creative enterprises, and facilitate the protection of intellectual property. Offer tax incentives to companies that invest in research and development of new products and designs. This could include tax deductions or credits for design and innovation expenses, thereby facilitating investments in creative activities. Create specific grant funds for design projects, especially for start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises. These funds could cover part of the development and registration costs of new designs, making the process less burdensome for creators. Invest in design education in schools and universities to promote awareness and competence in this field. Organize workshops, seminars, and professional training courses to update designers and entrepreneurs on the latest trends and technologies in the design sector. Establish or enhance regional design centers that act as hubs for collaboration, innovation, and resource sharing

among companies, designers, and research institutes. These centers could offer access to advanced technologies, shared workspaces, and legal and commercial consulting services. Promote Italian design nationally and internationally through marketing campaigns, industry fairs, and exhibitions. This would help local businesses gain greater visibility and expand their markets. Encourage partnerships between academic institutions and industries to transfer knowledge and innovations from academia to the market. These collaborations can accelerate the development of new designs and increase the rate of design registrations. Simplify the design registration process and reduce associated costs. Ensure that intellectual property rights are effectively protected and that there is a legal system that supports creators in defending their designs from unauthorized use. Adapt support policies to the specific context of each region, considering its dominant industries and the particular needs of its entrepreneurs and designers. For example, regions with a strong presence in the fashion sector could benefit from specific incentives for fashion design.

Conclusions. Design applications in Italian regions increased by an average of 4.53% between 2018 and 2023. This value also grew in Southern Italy with a value of +15.36% and in the Center with +4.15%. Design applications in the North decreased between 2018 and 2023 by an amount equal to -0.01%. However, if we look at 2023, we can notice a significant inequality between the Italian macro-regions. The leading region for design applications is the Center, followed by the North. Southern Italy, on the other hand, is significantly behind with a value equal to 50.43% of the North and 45.46% of the Center.

Declarations

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Appendix

